

PREDICTION OF PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF BIS-CARBAMATE MEE-2 AND ITS DERIVATIVES

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Abstract. In this research work, the biological activities of bis-carbamate MEE-2 and its derivatives were studied in the online pass online virtual screening program for the pharmaceutical and medical industries. As a result of screening, many pharmacotherapeutic activities were identified with a high percentage of the presence of various cytochromes as inhibitors, agonists and substrates. The data obtained will help for further research on these compounds and their use in pharmacology.

Key words: Bis-carbamate, pass online, screening, agonist, activity, medical, biological, virtual, cytochromes.

Introduction. Carbamates, or urethanes, are organic compounds with the general formula $R'R''NCOOR$ derived from carbamic acid (carbonic acid amide). Currently, many studies in the field of carbamates and derivatives of bis-carbamates are awakened not only by theoretical, but also by practical needs. From this point of view, carbamates and derivatives of bis-carbamates are undoubtedly of interest as substances with biological and pharmacological activity [4,5]. The use of these substances in medicine as anti-viral, anti-tumor, anti-inflammatory, anti-arrhythmic and other drugs is of particular interest. Also, representatives of this class of chemical compounds exhibit broad biological activity, due to which they are used as additives and medicines (for example, proserine and carbacholine). This list could be continued, as the geography of application of carbamates, bis-carbamates and polyurethane derivatives is wide. That's why we decided to conduct analyzes with the help of "Computer chemistry" and "Mathematical chemistry" programs, which are currently developing rapidly. In computer chemistry, substances (molecules) are modeled according to molecular graphs, with formal operations on the change of

substances (chemical reactions). In chemistry, this approach greatly simplifies the algorithmization of chemical problems, reduces them to typical problems of combinatorics and discrete mathematics, and allows searching for solutions using computer programs [1-3]. As examples of typical tasks of computer chemistry, we can cite the following: search for "structure-activity" relationships; creating sets of chemical structures that meet the specified parameters (composition, presence of functional groups, etc.); listing various chemical reactions between given reagents (called "computational synthesis") and so on [6,9-11]. The authors of this article synthesized bis-carbamates of the MEE series [20-23]. For example scheme for the synthesis of bis-carbamate N,N'-hexamethylene bis-[(meta-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2:

The mechanism and parameters influencing the reaction have been studied [16,18]. MOL file model of bis-carbamate MEE-2 for Pass online program (fig. 1):

Figure 1. MolView (model) of bis-carbamate MEE-2

The resulting product was studied in international chemical databases [8]. We present to you the initial calculations of the bis-carbamate molecule MEE-2 using Pass online program (Table 1):

Table 1

Preliminary description of the compound MEE-2

 Compound MEE-2	Formula		$C_{22}H_{28}N_2O_4$
	Molecular weight		384.4742 u
	Hydrogen bond donors		2
	Hydrogen bond acceptors		4
	Percent composition		
	C	$12.0107 \text{ u} \times 22$	68.727 %
	H	$1.00794 \text{ u} \times 28$	7.3406 %
	N	$14.0067 \text{ u} \times 2$	7.2863 %
O	$15.9994 \text{ u} \times 4$	16.646 %	

The aim of this research work was to predict the pharmacological, therapeutic and medicinal activities of compounds of the MEE series by the structure-based in silico "structure-activity" method in the PASS program.

Materials and Methods. Synthesis of N,N'-hexamethylene bis-[(m-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2: In a three-neck flask equipped with a reflux condenser, a thermometer, and a stirrer, place 7.70 g (0.02 mol) of meta-cresol, add 30 ml of triethylamine (TEA), 60 ml of dimethylformamide (DMF), add drops at a temperature of 40-42 °C with stirring 2.6 ml hexamethylene diisocyanate (HMDI) dissolved in 8 ml DMF. The reaction mixture is stirred for 3 hours at a reaction mixture temperature of 45-48 °C. After the time has passed, the contents of the flask are transferred to a glass and water is added. The deposited precipitate is washed with those. After drying, a colorless powder is obtained with a yield of 9.6 g (93.7% of theoretical). $T_{\text{melt}} = 201\text{--}202^\circ\text{C}$; $R_f = 0.74$; $M_M = 468.64$; Found, %: C – 71.74; H – 8.51; N – 5.98; Calculated, %: C – 71.76; H – 8.60; N – 5.97.

Virtual screening of structural formulas based on "Structure-Activity" (SAR) relationship PASS Online <http://way2drug.com/PassOnline/predict.php> computer prediction program to find directions of practical use of new substances. Substances under study: N,N'-hexamethylene bis-[(meta-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2; N,N'-hexamethylene N,N'-dinitroso bis-[(meta-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2a; N,N'-hexamethylene N,N'-disodium bis-[(meta-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2b; N,N'-hexamethylene N,N'-diisopropyl bis-[(meta-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2v; N,N'-

hexamethylene N,N'-dichloro bis-[(meta-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2g; N,N'-hexamethylene N,N'-dibenzyl bis-[(meta-cresol)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2d.

Results and Discussions. PASS Online predicts over 3500 kinds of biological activity, including pharmacological effects, mechanisms of action, toxic and adverse effects, interaction with metabolic enzymes and transporters, influence on gene expression, etc. To obtain the predicted biological activity profile for your compound, only structural formula is necessary; thus, prediction is possible even for virtual structure designed in computer but not synthesized yet [12,15,17,19]. We have decided to present only those pharmacotherapeutic activities that are most likely to exist (Table 2).

Table 2

**Availability of estimated biological activities of synthesized substances
for medicine and pharmacology - (Pa >60%)**

Substances	Activities	Pa
MEE-2	CDP-glycerol glycerophosphotransferase inhibitor	0,846
	Against eczema	0,808
MEE-2a	CYP2F1 substrate	0,767
	TP53 expression enhancer	0,640
MEE-2b	CYP2C12 substrate	0,867
	General anesthesia	0,734
	Antiseborrheic	0,743
MEE-2v	CYP2C12 substrate	0,844
	Antidyskinetic	0,713
	Antihypoxic	0,667
MEE-2g	CYP2C12 substrate	0,867
	Acaricide	0,628
	Against infection	0,615
	Antiseptic	0,600
MEE-2d	Taurine dehydrogenase inhibitor	0,768
	1,4-lactonase inhibitor	0,675
	Fibrinolytic	0,618

*Note: Pa - The probability that an activity exists.

According to predictions of Table 2, compound MEE-2a showed the highest result of CYP2F1 substrate 0.767 (76%) and TP53 expression enhancer 0.640 (64%), compound MEE-2 showed result CDP-glycerol glycerophosphotransferase inhibitor 0.846 (84%) and against eczema 0,808 (80%). All substances of the MEE series showed high activities as substrates of CYP2F1, CYP2C12. Compound MEE-2d showed inhibitor of taurine dehydrogenase and 1,4-lactonase. Also, substances MEE-2v and MEE-2g showed antidyskinetic 0,713 (71%), antihypoxic 0,667 (66%) and against infection 0,615 (61%), antiseptic 0,600 (60%) activities.

Conclusion. The pharmacokinetic and pharmacotherapeutic parameters of bis-carbamate MEE-2 and its derivatives were predicted, and in silico screening of biological activity for medicine were carried out. Virtual PASS screening revealed that all bis-carbamates can act as CYP2F1, CYP2C12 substrates as well as CDP-glycerol glycerophosphotransferase, taurine dehydrogenase and 1,4-lactonase inhibitors. The results show that MEE series bis-carbamates and its derivatives exhibit a wide range of in silico activities and can be used for the synthesis of potential bioactive compounds and used in pharmacology.

References

1. American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH). 2003. Guide to Occupational Exposure Values. Cincinnati, OH. <https://dhss.delaware.gov/dph/files/carbamfaq.pdf>
2. Emon N.U., Alam S, Rudra S., et al. Antidepressant, anxiolytic, antipyretic, and thrombolytic profiling of methanol extract of the aerial part of Piper nigrum: In vivo, in vitro, and in silico approaches. Food Sci. Nutr., 2021, 9(2): 833-846.
3. Ochoa M.E., Farfán N., Labra-Vázquez P., et al. Synthesis, characterization and in silico screening of potential biological activity of 17 α -ethynyl-3 β , 17 β , 19-trihydroxyandrost-5-en acetylated derivatives. Journal of Molecular Structure, 2021, 1225: 129167.
4. Maxsumov A.G., Mashayev E.E., Shapatov F.U., Azamatov O'.R., Ismailov B.M. N, N'-geksametilen bis-[(o-, m-krezolilo)-karbamat] larning o'tkir toksikligini o'rganish // Universal journal of medical and natural sciences. 2023. Vol.1, Issue 7, pp. 53-61.

5. Eldor Mashaev Ergashvoy ogli, Feruz Shapatov Utaganovich, & Bakhtiyar Kenjaev Ismatovich. (2023). In silico and in vivo study of acute toxicity of the substance of the MEE series. *Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing*, 1(8), 46–48.

6. E. E. Mashaev, A. G. Makhsumov, F. U. Shapatov “Study of the biostimulatory properties of MEE series bis-carbamates”, Vol. 2 No. 11 (2023): *International Journal of Agrobiotechnology and Veterinary Medicine*, pp. 1–4.

7. Yergaliyeva, E., Bazhykova, K., Abeuova, S., Vazhev, V., & Langer, P. (2022). In silico drug-likeness, biological activity and toxicity prediction of new 3,5-bis(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-4H-pyran-4-one derivatives. *Chemical Bulletin of Kazakh National University*, 107(4), 14-20.

8. E.E. Mashaev, I.R. Asqarov, M.M. Xojimatov, and M.M. Muminjonov, “Classification of bis-carbamates of the MEE series based on the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity of the republic of Uzbekistan”, *JNCI*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 97–103, Dec. 2023.

9. Машаев Элдор, Махсумов Абдухамид, and Иброхим Абдугафуров. “In silico исследование бис-карбаматов серии МЭЭ на органоспецифической канцерогенности для крыс”. *Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, vol. 35, no. 2, Dec. 2023, pp. 95-99.

10. Машаев Элдор, Махсумов Абдухамид, and Мухиддинов Баходир. “In silico изучение экотоксичности бис-карбаматов серии МЭЭ”. *Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, vol. 35, no. 2, Dec. 2023, pp. 100-103.

11. Машаев Элдор, Махсумов Абдухамид, and Шодиев Абдурасул. “Прогнозирование острой токсичности бис-карбаматов серии МЭЭ на крысах”. *Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, vol. 35, no. 2, Dec. 2023, pp. 104-108.

12. Хайруллина В.Р., Герчиков А.Я., and Зарудий Ф.С.. "Анализ взаимосвязи «Структура-ингибирующая активность циклооксигеназы-2» в ряду производных ди-трет-бутилфенола, тиазолон и оксазолон" *Вестник Башкирского университета*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2014, pp. 417-423.

13. Махсумов Абдухамид Гафурович, Мухиддинов Баходир Фахриддинович, Машаев Элдор Эргашвой Угли, Абсалямова Гулноза Маматкуловна and Исмаилов Бобурбек Махмуджанович. "Изучение острой

токсичности субстанции МЭЭ-2" *Universum: химия и биология*, no. 1(115), 2023, pp. 32-35. DOI - 10.32743/UniChem.2024.115.1.16584

14. Махсумов Абдухамид Гафурович, Муҳиддинов Баходир Фахриддинович, Машаев Элдор Эргашвой Угли, Исмаилов Бобурбек Махмуджанович and Хакимова Гузал Рахматовна. "In silico, in vitro изучение биологических активностей препаратов серии МЭЭ-1,2,3" *Universum: химия и биология*, no. 1(115), 2023, pp. 52-56. DOI - 10.32743/UniChem.2024.115.1.16531

15. Filimonov D.A., Lagunin A.A., Glorizova T.A., Rudik A.V., Druzhilovskii D.S., Pogodin P.V., Poroikov V.V. (2014). Prediction of the biological activity spectra of organic compounds using the PASS online web resource. *Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds*, 50 (3), 444-457.

16. E. Mashaev, A. Makhsumov, Bahodir Fakhriddinov, and F. Khudoyberdiev, "Study of the biological activities of bis-carbamates of the MEE series for the agricultural industry", *ERUS*, vol. 2, no. 16, pp. 803–807, Dec. 2023.

17. Zakharov A.V., Lagunin A.A., Filimonov D.A., Poroikov V.V. (2012). Quantitative prediction of antitarget interaction profiles for chemical compounds. *Chemical Research in Toxicology*, 25 (11) 2378-2385.

18. Eldor Mashaev, Umidjon Beshimov, & Abduhamid Makhsumov. (2023). Mass spectroscopic study of bis-carbamate MEE-1 by in silico method. *World scientific research journal* (cc. 108–113). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394286>

19. Filimonov D.A., Zakharov A.V., Lagunin A.A., Poroikov V.V. (2009). QNA based "Star Track" QSAR approach. *SAR and QSAR in Environmental Research*, 20 (7-8), 679-709.

20. Eldor Mashaev, Abduhamid Makhsumov, Odil Ziyadullaev, Guzal Otamukhamedova. "Studying the structure of bis-carbamate of the MEE series by IR spectral analysis method" *Science and innovation*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2024, pp. 85-90. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10511127>

21. Eldor Mashaev, Abduhamid Makhsumov, & Akhmadali Khudoyberdiev. (2024). Study of the synthesis of bis-carbamate of the MEE series and study of brutto inhibitory activity. *Journal of science-innovative research in Uzbekistan*, 2(1), pp. 318–324. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10521571>

22. Eldor Mashaev, Feruz Shapatov “Prediction of pharmacotherapeutic activities of bis-carbamates of the MEE series”, IQRO, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 50–54, Jan. 2024.

23. E. Mashaev, U. Azamatov and Sh. Jo’raqulov “Synthesis and study of the properties of bis-carbamate MEE-2 and its derivatives”, ERUS, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 180–185, Jan. 2024.

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